

Influence of working-class mothers on academic performance of primary school pupils in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of working-class mothers on the academic performance of primary school pupils in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Three research question and three corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study and the population consisted of all primary schools' working-class mothers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Random sampling method was adopted in selecting 17 primary schools in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Purposive sampling approach was used to select 10 working-class mothers from each of the school chosen for the study thereby giving a sample size of 170 working-class mothers. The instrument for the study was a questionnaire titled: Influence of Working-Class Mothers Inventory (IWCMI). Validity of the research instrument was done by experts, suggestions made were incorporated into the final draft of the instrument. Reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Descriptive statistics were used to answer the research questions while Independent Sample Test (IST) and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation statistics were used to test the hypotheses. The outcome of the study revealed, among others, that the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance is high. Conclusion was reached and useful recommendation made which included that working-class mothers should be selective in their choice of job to reduce the influences of careers on pupils' academic performance.

Keywords: working class mothers, pupils, academic performance

Introduction

Traditional family roles are changing as democratic notions sink into the social system. Earlier, it was assumed that man was the main provider in the family and that the rudimentary social roles of mothers are to bear and raise children. However, mothers are beginning to realize that there is a world outside their kitchen windows (Lavanya, 2022). The major social change in the twentieth century was the entrance of mothers into the world of work. Significant social and personal adjustments are therefore necessary for working-class mothers to cope with such changes in their career parts.

One could define a working-mother as a woman with the ability to combine a vocation with the additional responsibility of raising children. The broad term may encompass two different categories of working women: the stay at a home mother who works from home and the woman who works away from home while managing to fulfill her maternal duties (Lavanya, 2022).

World Bank (2024) reported female labor force (% of total labor force) in Nigeria to be 43.89 % in 2022. In 2023, the labor force participation rate for the female population in Nigeria was estimated at slightly over 52 percent. That year, the labor force participation rate reached nearly 57 percent for mothers 15 years or older (Sasu, 2023), most of them with children and, or husband at home.

Material aspirations and the necessities of daily life often compel both parents to work. Improved educational opportunities for mothers have led to rapid increase in the number of employed mothers both in public and private sectors. A qualified woman may insist on working to maintain an effective career and be financially independent. The single working mother is a combination of these entities, working not only to run the family but also to maintain her position as a financially independent head of the family (Lavanya, 2022). Mothers are also turning out in large numbers in the workforce due to economic necessity. While people may be willing to accept the idea of career women, they are not willing to excuse them from their duties as career moms (Lavanya, 2022). The economic downturn, the desire for career pursuance, and global advocacy for gender equality have all contributed to an increase in the number and percentage of mothers in the labour force (Dimkpa, 2010; Ajala, 2017). These variables are the result of women's desires for financial independence, self-worth, and, most

importantly, the dismantling of the ingrained notion of the "glass ceiling" that prohibits them from holding professional positions (Agarwal & Lenka, 2015; Rajora, 2019; Young et al., 2021).

The socioeconomic statuses of employed mothers usually influence primary school pupils' academic performances. Igube and Ejaro (2003) investigated the influence of working-class mothers, family instability and children's education, and discovered that working class mothers often neglect primary school pupils' welfare as a result of their careers. According to them, about one-third of the working-class mothers' children suffered as a result of this neglect, and that it is a matter of concern that about 22 percent of the pupils experienced health problems due to mothers' neglect, and poor nutrition often results in ill health. The combination of poor feeding and ill health are likely to have a negative impact on the children's education.

A study by Nomaguchi and Milkie (2006) examined whether or not people's perceptions of their parents was affected by their mother's employment (or lack thereof) during their childhood. Regardless of hours worked, children of mothers who worked reported less discipline from their mothers than those whose mothers did not work outside the home. Those with working class mothers also reported less support and more verbal assaults than those whose mothers did not work (Nomaguchi and Milkie, 2006). A study by Gennetian, Lopoo, and London (2008) used statistics gathered in a survey of urban mothers to assess how mothers' work affected adolescents' school performance and participation in school-related activities. They found that children of stay-at-home mothers were more likely to have above average school performance and to skip school than children of non-working class.

In most developing countries, such as Nigeria, employment relationships are structured according to gender norms, resulting in the disproportionate subjugation of mothers because men are socialized to be breadwinners, while mothers are always expected to care for the home (Abubakar, 2018). Now that many of these mothers have paid jobs, they have not abandoned their roles in their families (Kayode, Ojo, & Adeoye, 2012; Nnubia & Okechukwu, 2022), and these cause some situations such as overloading of roles. Even if they do not work outside the home, mothers are likely to be strained by household tasks, motherhood, and being a wife (Hegewisch & DuMonthier, 2016; Rajgariah, Chandrashekar Appa, Babu, Gopi, Ramaiha, & Kumar., 2021). Conversely, the burden of dual full-time work, working mother's physical, emotional, and mental well-being, as well as their productivity, is negatively impacted by gender norms at home and at work (Roberts, 2014; Uwannah, Egwuonwu & James, 2022) thereby, making them to be more vulnerable to pressures resulting from perceived "maternal walls," which limit their job options once they have children (Thakur, Bansal. & Maini, 2018).

According to Ademuyiwa, Dahunsi, Adetunji and Adeniran (2022), mothers' dual roles are often in conflict with one another because they divide their time and energy between the two spheres of activity. Work-family conflict can as well be exacerbated by long working hours, inflexibility, and a less pleasant work environment, particularly in the lives of working mothers whose children are poorly spaced and are of school age (Lupu et al., 2018; Owodunni, 2022). Working mothers who were exhausted have little or no time to care for themselves as a result of the conflict between work and family life (De Ravindranath, Karter-Sing, Arumugam, & Kularajasing, 2021). Ajala (2017) also noted that a typical working mother or career woman experiences conflicting role expectations while at work and at home, including having to manage primary school pupils' tasks, careers, and social circles, which present them with challenges.

Working moms in Nigeria feels they are being forced back to work too early, risking their and their babies' health (Lawal, 2022). Mother's job stress, long working hours, and lack of sleep may cause poor quality of time spend with her child (Gordon, 2007; Amede, 2017). Stephiana, et al., (2019) conducted a study to analyses the possible effects of maternal employment on child growth in the early period of life (0-3 years) and found that the higher was the cognitive score; the lower was the average mother's working hours. She concluded that mother's presence at home, focus on the family and children at early period of child's growth years can improve child growth and quality of children's development. The cognitive effects could still be seen by age seven or eight. Mothers, in spite of having their kid's best interests at heart, might fail to provide them with safe emotional outlet when professionally engaged with jobs (Metilda & Meheswariet, 2015; Amede, 2023).

Papalia and Martorell (2014) discovered that the interaction between mother and child has a direct impact on child's cognitive development. Simen (2022) listed 6 ways to balance life as working mothers to include have an answer for "why, clarify what "mom" means to you, invest in good help, look for the energy traps among others. Ofei, Kwashie., Asiedua, Serwaa and Akotiah (2018) discovered that time management and priority setting would help working mothers cope with the demands of their jobs. Bakker and de Vries, (2021) note that organizational resources such as human resource practices which may include employing social workers and also having a counselling unit in the organization will help mothers to cope better with stress

Empirical studies reviewed so far on this theme had revealed contradictory conclusions. This made this study necessary to carry out similar research in a unique environment to see whether the findings would support or contradict the existing knowledge. This study therefore examined the influence of working-class mothers on academic performance of primary school pupils in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Throughout history mothers have been regarded as the weaker gender, both physically and intellectually. As a result, women's roles tended to center around the home and raising children. Over time mother have gradually entered the workforce and have gained increasingly prestigious positions. With more mothers currently in the workforce than ever before, fewer children are being raised by stay-at-home mothers and more are spending prolonged hours at childcare facilities.

Children with working class mothers are usually placed in group childcare, which results in reduced maternal attachment and poor mental development. This may have significant cognitive and affective deficit later in childhood. Working class mothers has contributed to lack of proper motherly care which results at times to permanent physical handicap, deprived cognitive and moral development, poor language formation and inadequate communication skills. The purpose of this study therefore was to examine the influence of working-class mothers on academic performance of primary school pupils in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Objective of the Study

The study examined the influence of working-class mothers on academic performance of primary school pupils in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Specific objectives include to:

1. Assess the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.
2. Determine the factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed.
3. Investigate the solution to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State
4. Evaluate the difference between job status of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.
5. Examine the difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.
6. Investigate the relationship between age job status, age stratifications and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State?
2. What are the factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed?
3. What are the solution to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significance difference between job statuses of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.
2. There is no significance difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.
3. There is no significance relationship between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey design to examine the study variables. Descriptive survey design allows the researcher to gather information, summarize, present and construe for the purpose of clarification. In this study the population consisted of all primary schools' staff, including working class mothers out of the available 300 in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Random sampling method was adopted in selecting 17 primary schools out of the existing 39 while purposive sampling approach was used to select 10 working class mothers from each of the school depicted for the study, giving a sample size of 170 participants. This sample size was adequate because according to Asika (1991), 10% element selected randomly from a population is to all intents and purposes deemed to be representative of the population and the findings from a study of that sample can be generalized for the population.

The instrument for the study was: Influence of Working-Class Mothers Inventory (IWCMI). The inventory was designed by the researcher and divided into four sections. A sought for the demographic data of respondents, Section B sought information relating to impact of working-class mothers on pupils' academic performance, Section C deals with factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed while Section D addresses issues on the solution to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance. The questionnaire adopted 4-point scale. The weighted mean of 2.5 was used as the bench mark for assessing the instrument.

To determine the validity of the research instruments, the inventory was validated by experts in the field of education, and suggestions made were incorporated into the final draft of the instrument to ensure its validity. The instrument used was trial-tested with twenty (20) staff in Ndokwa west Local Government Area of Delta State, which was outside the original sample population and their responses collected. Reliability coefficient obtained of 0.87 was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

The questionnaire was personally administered to the respondents and subsequently collected. However, 160 (constituted 95%) of the 170 questionnaires administered were retrieved and utilized for data analysis. The data collected were analyzed with descriptive statistics, Independent Sample Test (IST) and the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation statistics. Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant levels.

Results

Research questions 1: What are the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State?

Impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance						Remark
S/N	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation		
Q1	Lack of quality time with primary school pupils at home to encourage academic growth. 160	497.00	3.1063	.30912		Agreed
Q2	Career mothers hardly pay attention to children nutritional needs that enhance their cognitive development. 160	497.00	3.1063	.30912		Agreed
Q3	Working class mothers hardly satisfy the emotional needs of primary school pupils 160	499.00	3.1188	.32451		Agreed
Q4	Career mothers seldom teach primary school pupils at home 160	491.00	3.0688	.31963		Agreed
Q5	Working class mothers' denial children of some rights and opportunities for to excel in school 160	501.00	3.1312	.33873		Agreed
Q6	vocational mothers hardly ever attend school PTA meetings to contribute to school welfare 160	491.00	3.0688	.29930		Agreed
Q7	Improper models to children affect children morals 160	492.00	3.0750	.30817		Agreed
Q8	Indiscipline encourages anti-social behaviour in schools 160	486.00	3.0375	.24795		Agreed
Q9	Deprivations of maternal attachment affect children self-concept in class activities 160	486.00	3.0375	.29434		Agreed

Q10	Working class mothers have little time moderate primary school pupils peer relations	160	447.00	2.7937	.65490	Agreed
	Total	1600	4887	3.05	.34	Agreed

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

Source: Field work, 2024

Table 1 revealed the descriptive statistics on the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The total score is 4887; an average score of 3.05 and Standard Deviation of .34. The total average is 3.05, is above the weighted mean of 2.5. The implication is that the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State is high.

Research Question 2: What are the factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed?

Table 2: Mean rating on the factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed

S/N	Factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Q11	Inadequate time to attend family events due to their busy schedules	160	490.00	3.0625	.24282	Agreed
Q12	Working class mothers are often tired and stressed up	160	501.00	3.1312	.33873	Agreed
Q13	They often suffer financial constraints	160	499.00	3.1188	.32451	Agreed
Q14	They are also prone to health issues	160	444.00	2.7750	.54887	Agreed
Q15	Susceptible to expensive child care	160	490.00	3.0625	.24282	Agreed
Q16	Suffer from gender discrimination	160	444.00	2.7750	.62395	Agreed
Q17	Disparity in salaries in favour of the male counterpart	160	484.00	3.0250	.31623	Agreed
Q18	Physical and mental attack	160	484.00	3.0250	.35378	Agreed
Q19	Insufficient maternity leave	160	468.00	2.9250	.34659	Agreed
Q20	Fixed working hours	160	454.00	2.8375	.51258	Agreed
	Total	160	4758	2.97	.39	Agreed

Source: Field work, 2024

Table 2 revealed mean rating on the factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed. Working class mothers are often tired and stressed up tops the list with a mean of 3.13, followed by They often suffer financial constraints, closely followed by inadequate time to attend family events due to their busy schedules, and Susceptible to expensive child care, Physical and mental attack, insufficient maternity leave and fixed working hours with mean scores of 3.11, 3.06, 3.02, 2.93 and 2.84 respectively. The total average is 2.97, is above the bench mark of 2.5. The implication is that there are many factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed.

Research question 3: What are the solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on the solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

S/N	Solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Q21	Accepting types job that create time for the family.	160	458.00	2.8625	.46901	Agreed

Q22	Maintaining regular communication with children to determine areas of needs	160 491.00	3.0688	.29930	Agreed
Q23	Checking children class work regularly	160 476.00	2.9750	.27357	Agreed
Q24	Ensuring proper discipline on children	160 493.00	3.0813	.35416	Agreed
Q25	Accepting jobs that are of close proximity to residential homes	160 494.00	3.0975	.42154	Agreed
Q26	time management and priority	160 444.00	2.7750	.54887	Agreed
Q27	Ask for maternal leave when necessary	160 498.00	3.1125	.24282	Agreed
Q28	Share your concerns with managers, co-worker and friends	160 459.00	2.8750	.62395	Agreed
Q29	Hiring home teachers to children after school hours	160 484.00	3.0250	.31623	Agreed
Q30	Moderating peer influence on children	160 484.00	3.0250	.35378	Agreed
	Total	160 4781	2.99	.39	

Source: Field work, 2024

Table 3 revealed the Descriptive statistics on the solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The total score is 4781; average score of 2.99 and standard Deviation of .39. The total average is 2.99, is above the bench mark of 2.5. The implication is that there are numerous the solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significance difference between job statuses of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Table 4: T-test analysis on the difference between job statuses of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	df	T	Sig.
Full-time	108	1.2778	.44999	.04330	158	12.62	.000
Part-time	52	2.2115	.41238	.05719			

At .05 significant level. Source: Field work, 2024.

The result in Table 4 above revealed a t-test statistics on the between job statuses of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State., at $t(-12.62, df= 158, P<05)$. The null hypothesis 1 which states that there is no significance difference between job statuses of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State was therefore rejected. The implication is that there is a significant difference between job statuses of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State as indicated in their mean proximity of 1.28 and 2.21 for full time and part-time working-class mothers respectively.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significance difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Table 5: Descriptive statistic on the difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Min	Max
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
20-30years	78	1.00	0.00000	0.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.00	1.00

31-40years	71	1.58	0.49748	0.0590	1.4597	1.6952	1.00	2.00
41years and above	11	2.00	0.00000	0.0000	2.0000	2.0000	2.00	2.00
Total	160	1.33	0.46985	0.0371	1.2516	1.3984	1.00	2.00

Source: Field work, 2024

Table 5 above depicts a Descriptive statistic on the difference between the age stratification of working-class mothers on children academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The table gives categories of age stratification of working-class mothers into 20-30years, 31-40years and 41years and above. A total of 160 working class mothers participated in the study. Out of this figure, 78 of them were within the range of 20-30years, 71 were of 31-40years and 11 were of 41years and above. The mean scores for the 20-30years, 31-40years and 41years and above are 1.00, 1.58 and 2.00 respectively; with a total mean score of 1.33.

Table 6: One-way ANOVA statistic on the difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

Status	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	17.776	2	8.888	80.549	.000
Within Groups	17.324	157	.110		
Total	35.100	159			

05 level of significant.

Source: Field work, 2024

The one-way ANOVA statistics revealed a significant difference between groups and within groups as shown in Table 6 above with F (80.549= df, 2/159, p = .000. The hypothesis which states that there is no significance difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State was therefore rejected. A posteriori in Table 4.11 was tested to determine the degree of differences between the categories of age stratifications. The mean differences for 20-30years are .58 and 1.00 to 31-40years and 41years and above respectively. 31-40years differ by .58 and .42 to 20-30years and 41years and above respectively while 41years and above differences to 20-30years and 31-40years are 1.00 and .42 respectively. The implication is that there is a significance difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Table 7: Tukey HSD Multiple Comparisons on the difference between age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significance relationship between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-

(I) Age	(J) Age	Mean Difference			95% Confidence Interval	
		(I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
20-30years	31-40years	-.57746*	.05449	.000	-.7064	-.4485
	41years and above	-1.00000*	.10699	.000	-1.2531	-.7469
31-40years	20-30years	.57746*	.05449	.000	.4485	.7064
	41years and above	-.42254*	.10764	.000	-.6772	-.1679
41years and above	20-30years	1.00000*	.10699	.000	.7469	1.2531
	31-40years	.42254*	.10764	.000	.1679	.6772

*. **The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.** **Source: Field work, 2024**

class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Table 8: Pearson Correlation on the relationship between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

		Status	Age	Qualifications
Status	Pearson Correlation	1	.709**	.604**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	160	160	160
Age	Pearson Correlation	.709**	1	.646**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	160	160	160
Qualifications	Pearson Correlation	.604**	.646**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	160	160	160

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field work, 2024

A Pearson product-moment correlation was run to determine the relationship between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The analysis revealed a positive correlation between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State, which was statistically significant ($r = .604^{**}$, $n = 160$, $p = .001$). The implication is that there is a positive correlation between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

Discussion of Findings.

Research question 1 sought to determine the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The analysis concluded that the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State Is high. This finding concurred with the views of Han, Waldfogel, and Brooks-Gunn (2001) who found that mothers entering the workforce, and that maternal employment in the first year of a child's life had a negative effect on cognitive outcomes for the child by age three or four. Children of employed mothers were also found to be more likely to skip school than children of non-working-class mothers (Gennetian, Lopoo, and London, 2008). Mother's job stress, long working hours, and lack of sleep may cause poor quality of time spend with her child (Gordon, 2007). Moreover, the child may start arguing with the family members on nominal things and turn rebellious and rude in nature (Almani et al., 2012). Stephiana, et al., (2019) conducted a study to establish the possible effects of maternal employment on child growth in the early period of life (0-3 years) and found that the higher was the cognitive score, the lower was the average mother's working hours. She concluded that mother's presence at home, focus on the family and children at early period of child's growth years can improve child growth and quality of children's development.

Research question 2 states: What are the factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed? The study revealed that there are many factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed. The outcome of the study agreed with Roberts (2014) and Uwannah et al, (2022) who observed that burden of dual full-time work, working mother's physical, emotional, and mental well-being, as well as their productivity, is negatively impacted by gender norms at home and at work thereby making them to be more vulnerable to pressures resulting from perceived "maternal walls," which limit their job options once they have children (Thakur et al., 2018). According to Ademuyiwa et al., (2022), mothers' dual roles are often in conflict with one another because they divide their time and energy between the two spheres of activity. Work-family conflict can as well be exacerbated by long working hours, inflexibility, and a less pleasant work environment, particularly in the lives of working mothers whose children are poorly spaced and are of school age (Lupu et al., 2018; Owodunni, 2022). Working mothers who were exhausted have little or no time

to care for themselves as a result of the conflict between work and family life (De Ravindranath et al., 2021). Pareja and Lewis (2006) noted that factors exogenous to the school, such as family background characteristics in general and mothers' employment in particular, have been and continue to be extremely important attributes in determining poor pupils' academic outcomes. Igube and Ejaro (2003) investigated the influence between working class mothers, family instability and children's education, and discovered that working class mothers tended to neglect primary school pupils' welfare as a result of their work life.

Research question 3 sought to determine the solution to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The finding showed that there are numerous solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The finding buttresses the position of Papalia & Martorell (2014) who discovered that the interaction between mother and child has a direct impact on child's cognitive development. Simen (2022) listed 6 ways to balance life as working mothers to include have an answer for "why, clarify what "mom" means to you, invest in good help, look for the energy traps among others.

Hypothesis 1 and 2 found significance differences between job statuses of working-class mothers as well as age stratifications of working-class mothers and primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Full time working mothers were comparatively more depressed than those who worked for part time. According to Pelcovitz (2013), early full-time employment (relative to mothers who were not working outside the home) was associated with later risk for child behavioural difficulties. Mothers, in spite of having their kid's best interests at heart, might fail to provide their kids a safe emotional outlet when professionally engage with jobs (Metilda & Meheswari, 2015).

Implication for Counselling

The study examined the influence of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. The outcome of this study would encourage counsellors to devise strategies to ameliorate the influence of working-class mothers on children academic performance. The outcome of this study would equip counsellors with information needed to organize workshops and seminars for working class mothers to balance career with family affairs and maximize children academic performance.

Conclusion

The outcome of the study revealed that the impacts of job commitment of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance is high. There are many factors militating against academic performance of children whose mother are gainfully employed. There are numerous the solutions to the negative impacts of working-class mothers on primary school pupils' academic performance. There is a significant difference between job statuses and age stratifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State. Also, there is a positive correlation between job status, age stratifications, academic qualifications of working-class mothers and academic qualifications of working-class mothers on primary pupils' academic performance. However, working-class mothers should be selective in their choice of job to reduce the influences of careers on pupils' academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, recommendations were made:

1. Working-class mothers should be selective in their choice of job to reduce the influences of careers on pupils' academic performance.
2. Government should increase maternal leave from 3 months to 1 year to ameliorate the influences of working-class mothers on children academic performance
3. Working class mothers should be treated kindly and granted permission whenever requested to attend to their family needs.

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